

SHORT NOTES

PREPARATION OF URANIUM(IV) OXYACETATE

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Preparation of two hydrated uranium(IV) oxyacetate possessing the formula $\text{UO}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Tripathy *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 739) and $\text{UO}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Sahoo and Patnaik, *Curr. Sci.*, 1960, 29, 16) was reported earlier. As these compounds were obtained in fine state of division, considerable difficulty was experienced in the filtration process; further, as much of the uranium remained in solution, the product was never quantitative. The method described below obviates the difficulty of filtration and makes the yield almost quantitative.

As before, the solution of uranyl acetate was subjected to photochemical reduction on exposure to sunlight (*loc. cit.*). Distillation of the reduced solution was next carried out under reduced pressure at about 80° , when uranium(IV) oxyacetate was precipitated in a fine form. The distillation was continued till the solution left was just enough to keep the precipitate moist. The compound was dried in vacuum at room temperature. Analysis was carried out as described previously (*loc. cit.*). The data recorded in Tables I and II show that the compound obtained possesses the formula $\text{UO}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The molecular weight from the three prepared samples was calculated from the U_3O_8 obtained and the values found were 399.9, 400.4, and 399.6 in place of the theoretical value 399.

It may be noted that the different methods of preparation have given rise to compounds associated with different number of water molecules although the method of drying remains the same.

TABLE I
 $\text{UO}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

U(IV) content by KMnO_4 .			Acetate by hydrolysis.		
Taken.	Found.	Calc.	Taken.	Found.	Calc.
289.0 mg.	171.5 mg.	172.4 mg.	257.6 mg.	76.17 mg.	76.47 mg.
369.8	220.3	220.6	442.4	131.0	130.8
186.8	111.6	111.4	640.0	190.2	189.2

TABLE II
Estimation of carbon and hydrogen.

Compound taken.	Weight of water.		Weight of CO_2 .	
	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
136.8 mg.	27.6 mg.	27.8 mg.	61.0 mg.	61.4 mg.
91.0	18.2	18.47	40.0	40.14